

Rule of Law: An Indian Narratives in the Context of State of Assam

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Abstract

In recent past, there has been a substantial increase in concern for the rule of law. Rule of law in its other term, is a new 'lingua franca' of global moral thought. Rule of law, sometimes called 'the supremacy of law', provides the terrain of people's struggle for known principles of laws without the intervention of discretion in their application. Presently, rule of law is considered to be the pillars of modernity and widely considered necessary for sustained economic development, the implementation of democracy and the protection of human rights. Asian countries, on the other hand begun to focus on rule of law and good governance and the institutional reforms which is required to bring them about. The rule of law is no more the feature of the English political system but a profound discourse for Asiatic country like India where the political system had been imported, with or without modifications and consequently the subsequent encroachment upon the rule of law have taken place.

In several Asian countries, the post-colonial discourses and conflicts resulted in an attempt to inject local values into their legal system. The effect of globalization, rapid utilization of automated artificial intelligence in human life veers the edifice of rule of law. Though Article-14 of the Constitution of India narrate rule of law, yet the time is surely for construction of multicultural narratives of rule of law with the spirit of unity. The overall goal of this paper is to focus the inclusivity of rule of law in India and in Assam with mutual diversity among Asian countries.

Key words: Lingua franca, democracy, good governance, globalization, Artificial Intelligence

In the recent past, there has been a substantial increase in the concern for the rule of law. Rule of law in its other term may be said to be a new 'lingua franca'¹ of global moral thought. Rule of law, sometime called the "supremacy of law" provides the terrain of people's struggle for known principles of laws without the intervention of discretion in their application. Presently, rule of law is considered to be the pillars of modernity and widely considered necessary for sustained economic development. The narratives aided the implementation of democracy and the protection of human rights under the roof of one single concept on rule of law. In the words of Upendra Baxi, people's movement like from Mahatma Gandhi to Nelson Mandela or beyond have contributed enormously to ethical refinement of the notion of rule of law². Conclusively, he narrates that rule of law mark and map diverse human history and its mobility. Again, according to the World Justice Project (WJP), rule of law index, 2024, the rule of law now becomes weakened in majority of countries and suggested that this progress is slowing down in possible future. During the pandemic time due to covid, the overall declination of civil justice is pulled back. However, it cannot be denied that protecting democracy and human rights is the chief goal in context of modern concept of rule of law.

The rule of law stands as a cornerstone in the edifice of the modern world and also widely acknowledged as a fundamental element for economic prosperity, enhancement of present political system and safeguarding the concept of human rights. As the Asiatic countries championed the cause for legal system that are not only efficacious but also deeply resonant with their cultural narratives, hence the rule of law tried to integrated the diversified community of Asian countries with a spirit of unity and mutual respect. This research work uplifted the landscape of Asian Countries and rule of law that derive in diverse communities which not only governs but also galvanizes the spirit of unity and mutual respect. Focusing India, more particularly Assam, the north east corner of India, it is tried to examine the new diversion of rule of law which break up the concept of Dicey's theory on the edifice on local laws paving the layer of good governance.

Basically, it can be stated that rule of law is a fundamental principle that all people, institutions and entities are accountable to the same laws, which are publicly promulgated, equally enforced and independently adjudicated. It emphasizes the supremacy of the law over arbitrary power, ensuing equality before the law and fairness in its application. Conclusively, key aspects include accountability, just law, open government and accessible and impartial justice.

¹Rule of law by Ankita Gautam & Pragati Loomba

² Rule of Law in India, Theory & Practice. Upendra Baxi.

Dicey's theory on Rule of Law:

The doctrine of Rule of Law is ascribed to Dicey whose writing in 1885 included the following three distinct though kindred ideas in rule of law:

- **Absence of arbitrary power:** No man is above the law. No man is punishable except for a distinct breach of law established in an ordinary legal manner before ordinary courts. The government cannot punish anyone merely by its own fiat. Persons in authority in England do not enjoy wide, arbitrary or discretionary powers.
- **Equality before law:** Every man, whatever his rank or condition, is subject to the ordinary law and jurisdiction of the ordinary courts.
- **Individual liberties:** The general principles of the British Constitution, and especially the liberties of individual are judge-made, ie. are the result of judicial decisions in particular cases.³

The third principle is peculiar to England. In many modern written Constitutions, the basic rights of the people are guaranteed in the Constitution itself. Dicey's principle has been criticised by many people from various angles. But in substance, his emphasis on the whole is, in his enunciation of Rule of Law, in the absence of arbitrary power, equality before the law and legal protection to certain basic human rights and these ideas remain relevant and significance in every democratic country. It is also true that, dictated by needs of practical government, a number of exceptions have been engrafted on these ideas in modern democratic countries. As for example, the universal growth of broad discretionary powers of the administration and administrative tribunals become the normal feature in many democratic countries. Government intervention in many daily activities of the citizen is on the increase creating a possibility of arbitrariness in state action. Rule of law is useful as a counter to this situation. It is clear from above discussion that rule of law has no fixed commutation though its broad emphasis is on absence of any centre of unlimited or arbitrary power in the country, on proper structuring and control of power and absence of arbitrariness in the Government.

The bedrock of history on rule of law can be said to be an ancient ideal which was discussed by ancient Greek philosophers such as Plato and Aristotle around 350BC. Plato wrote "where the law is subject to some other authority and has none of its own, the collapse of the State, in my view, is not far off: but if law is the master of the Government and the Government is its slave, then the situation is full of promise and man enjoy all the blessings that the God shower on a state."

³ Indian Constitutional Law-M.P.Jain. Pub-N.M.Tripathi. Pvt.Ltd.4th

Aristotle endorsed the concept of rule of law by writing that “Law should govern and those in power should be servants of the law”. On the other hand, Sir Ivor Jennings characterized rule of law as “an unruly horse.”⁴

Rule of Law: Asian Narratives:

The Asian countries are championing the cause for legal systems that are not only efficacious but also deeply resonant with their unique cultural narratives. It is an undeniable fact that rule of law is one of the pillars of the modern world and is widely considered necessary for sustained economic development, the implementation of democracy and the protection of human rights. It has emerged in western liberal democracies and the question is how far it is likely to take root fully in the different cultural, economic and political context of Asia. The west has the law, order, rule, reason, rational bureaucracies, predictability and certainty. On the other hand, in some cases, Asian countries are seen as incapable of implementing ‘the rule of law’ or a modern legal system because of cultural factors. Side by side, the superiority of Western legal system is deemed to be justifying with a missionary like effort to transplant Western laws, institutions, norms and values to Asia.

The rapid change in many legal systems in Asia and the likelihood and further rapid development require new conceptual framework for understanding the purposes of law, the various roles of the legal systems, the ways in which they operate, and the development paths of legal institutions among Asian countries. Some argue that certain ‘Asian Values’ such as Confucianism, which emphasizes hierarchy and social order, might influence how the rule of law is perceived and applied. This can lead to different emphasis on individual rights versus collective well-being. Again, in some Asian Countries, especially those with rapid economic development, the focus may be on achieving economic growth, which can sometimes lead to prioritizing stability and order over individual liberties, there by potentially impacting the full implementation of rule of laws. Rule of law is an everchanging concept and the discourses on rule of law in Asia encompass multiple strands. There is a variety of conceptions within Asia and even within particular nations. Almost In all Asiatic states there is a tension between liberal democratic rule of law and alternatives that reflect local values, tradition and in many cases difference in level of economic development and institutional arrangements. Thus, for example in Philippines, one catches glimpses of an alternative redistributive conception in the way rule of law is frequently linked to social and political philosophies that promise justice, social welfare and people power democracy. Therefore, it is clear that the local diversity is ensured by the path-dependency and context specificity of rule of law and legal reforms.

Rule of Law: Indian discourse:

⁴ Supra 1

In India, the concept 'rule of law' formally gets its existence as a fundamental right under Article-14 of the Constitution of India. Article-14 of the Constitution of India speaks that the state shall not deny to any person equality before the law or the equal protection of the laws within the territory of India⁵. Article-14 of Indian Constitution based on the Dicey's principle of rule of law. The first expression "equality before the law" which is taken from the English common law, is a declaration of equality of all persons within the territory of India, implying thereby the absence of any special privilege in favour of any individual. Every person, whatever be his rank or position, is subject to the jurisdiction of the ordinary courts. The second expression, "the equal protection of the laws", which is rather a corollary of the first expression and is based on the last clause of the first section of the 14th amendment to the American Constitution, directs that equal protection shall be secured to all persons within the territorial jurisdiction of the Union in the enjoyment of their rights and privileges without favouritism or discrimination. It has been said that the equal protection of the laws is a pledge of protection or guarantee of equal laws. However, Article-14 does not rule out classification on reasonable ground. In *Kedar Nath Bajoria*⁶, the equal protection of laws guaranteed by Art. 14 of the Constitution does not mean that all the laws must be general in character and universal in application for the purpose of legislation.

First, 'equality before the law' does not mean that the 'powers of the private citizens are the same as the powers of the public officials. Secondly, 'the rule of law does not prevent certain classes of persons being subject to special rules. Article-361 of the Constitution of India provides that the President or the Governors of State shall not be answerable to any Court for the exercise and performance of the powers and duties of the office or for any act done or purporting to be done by him in the exercise and performance of those powers and duties. No criminal proceeding shall be instituted or continued against the President or the Governor of a State in any Court during his term of office. No process for the arrest or imprisonment of the President or the Governor of State shall be issued from any Court during his term of office. Thirdly, ministers and other executive bodies are given very wide discretionary powers by statute. A minister may be allowed by law 'to act as he thinks fit' or 'if he is satisfied'. However, such power is sometimes abused. Today, a large number of legislations are passed in the form of delegated legislation, i.e., rules, orders or statutory instruments made by ministers and other bodies and not directly by Parliament. These rules did not exist in Dicey's time. Fourthly, certain members of society are governed by special rules in their professions, i.e., lawyers, doctors, nurses, members of armed forces and police. Such classes of people are treated differently from ordinary citizens.

⁵ V.N. Shukla's Constitution of India. By Mahendra Singh. Eastern Book Company, Lucknow. 8th Edi. P.51

⁶ *Kedar Nath Bajoria vs. State of W.B.* AIR 1953 SC 404

It is an accepted truth that the Constitution of India itself recognize the exception to the rule of law as propounded by Dicey. There are certain provisions, which under certain circumstances, limit the effectiveness of Article-14. Thus,

1. The scope of right to equality under Article 14 has been considerably restricted by the 42nd Amendment Act, 1976. The new Article-31-C added by the Amendment Act provides that laws made by the State for implementing the Directive Principle contained in clause(b) or clause(c) of Article-39 cannot be challenged on the ground that they are violative of Article-14. Such laws will thus be an exception to Article 14 of the Constitution.⁷
2. Article 359(1) provides that where a proclamation of emergency is in operation the President may, by order, declare that the right to move any court for the enforcement of such rights conferred by Part-III shall remain suspended. Thus, if the President of India issues an order, where a proclamation of Emergency is in operation, enforcement of Article-14 may be suspended for the period during which the Proclamation is in force.
3. Article 361 lays down that the President and the Governors are exempted from any criminal proceeding during the tenure of their office.
4. Under International law, foreign sovereign and ambassadors enjoy full immunity from any judicial process. This is also available to enemy aliens for acts of war.

In India, the concept of Rule of law can be traced back to the period of Upanishad.⁸It provides that the law is the king of kings. It is more powerful and rigid than the king. There is nothing higher to or above law. Through rule of law, justice shall win since the weak shall prevail over the strong. The rule of law means that the law rules, which is based on the principles of freedom, equality, non-discrimination, fraternity, accountability and non-arbitrariness and is certain, regular and predictable, using the word law in the both the senses jus and lex. Thus, the key aspect of rule of law in ancient India was the dharma, customary law and the judicial system which was followed at that time.

However, the recent expansions of the concept of rule of law in every field of administrative operations have assigned it a place of special significance in the Indian administrative law. The Supreme Court of India, in the process of interpretation of rule of law vis-à-vis operation of administrative powers, in several recent cases, emphasized upon the need of fair and just procedure, adequate safeguards against

⁷ Sanjeev Coke Mfg. Co. V. Bharat Cooking Coal Ltd. (1983) 1scc 147

⁸ Rule of law by Ankita Gautam & Pragati Loomba in the book 'Comparative Public Law, edited by Dr. Arvindeka Chaudhary. Bharti publication. P.-108

any executive encroachment on personal liberty, free legal aid to the poor and speedy trial in criminal cases as necessary adjuncts to rule of law. Giving dissenting opinion in the death penalty case⁹, Justice Bhagwati explains fully the meaning of rule of law in the following words: "The rule of law permeates the entire fabric of the Constitution and indeed forms one of its basic features. The rule of law excludes arbitrariness, its postulate is 'intelligence without passion' and reason free from desire. Wherever we find arbitrariness or unreasonableness there is denial of the rule of law. Law in the context of rule of law does not mean any law enacted by legislative authority, howsoever arbitrary despotic it may be, otherwise even in dictatorship, it would be possible to say that there is rule of law, because every law made by the dictator, may be arbitrary and unreasonable, has to be obeyed in conformity with such law.

However the recent judicial pronouncements in India exhibit a dynamic and positive approach to the concept of rule of law by laying the need of the fair play and justice in every walk of administrative action. Judiciary has come forward to make judicial remedies available for all in order to uphold the human rights against any administrative erosions and to ensure safeguards the dignity of human in society.

Rule of Law: Discourse in context of Assam:

Assam, a tiny region of North East India is a place of diversity with integrity of different culture and customs with the challenges of illegal immigration, have reach a different level in case of establishing rule of law. Regarding the concept of rule of law in Assam like in other parts of India, operates within the framework of the Indian Constitution which ensures equality before the law and the supremacy of law. The supreme law emphasizes that the state will govern by law enacted by the Parliament which is consisting of the representatives elected, as per the provisions of the Constitution of India. The main challenges and discourses of rule of law in Assam is the task, mainly centralized by the ethnic diversity. Thus, in Assam, the rule of law stands at a critical crossroads between national security, ethnic diversity and democratic rights. However, the accountability of the government, in the present-day context arise in a new turning point depending upon the existing administrative pattern. With the advent of science and technology resulted the era of artificial intelligence in a new dimension resulting the transparency about rule of law which is at stake due to existing sovereignty and their rule.

It is an undeniable fact that Assam has unique socio-political and historical contexts that have shape its discourse on the rule of law-particularly in relation to issues like ethnic identity, migration, insurgency and problems regarding citizenship. Thus, Assam has a long history to be the home of diverse ethnic groups like Assamese, Bodo's, Nagas, Manipuri's, Mizo's and other ethnic groups which lead to a complex socio-ethnic relations. In the years from 1979 to 1985, the outbreak the Assam Movement, demanding the identification and expulsion of illegal migrants, was a key

⁹ Bachan Singh v. State of Punjab, A. I. R.1992.S.C.1325

event that raised serious questions about citizenship, legal rights and law enforcement in context of rule of law. The Assam Accord of 1985 on this issue sought to restore order and reinforce the rule of law with promise to identify and deport illegal migrants. On the line of the wish of people, the National Register of Citizens (NRC) updated under Supreme court supervision, aimed to determine the legality of citizen in Assam. However, due to lack of transparency, due process, these efforts also seem to lose the principle of natural justice.

Again in 2019, the existing Government bring a bill which had been enacted as Citizenship Amendment Act (CAA) which offers citizenship to non-Muslim immigrants from neighbouring country which is strongly opposed by the inhabitants of Assam, but in vain, resulting rule of law an uncontrolled shooting horse. The people of Assam already experienced with the decades of insurgency, draconian law like Armed Forces (Special Powers) Act, 1958, which lead to human rights violation and erosion of civil liberties, there by weakening the rule of law. It may be concluded that the rule of law in Assam exist within a fragile framework with the systematic challenges-ranging from ethnic divisions to policy maker with unaccountable show making. The comments of AI Grok about the sovereign head of the State reflected the fragile nature. Hence for a healthier rule of law discourse, inclusive governance, transparent legal processes and accountable institutions are utmost essential.